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**INFLUENCE OF INFORMATION COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY ON LEARNING PHYSICS
IN POST COVID-19 ERA IN JOS SOUTH, PLATEAU STATE, NIGERIA**

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ABSTRACT

The research explored the influence of information communication technology on learning physics in post covid-19 era in Jos South, Plateau State, Nigeria. The study was guided by three objectives and research questions respectively. A descriptive survey research design was adopted with a population of 5,500 students; 220 respondents were sampled using random sampling. Data was collected using questionnaire for students which was validated by experts and obtain a Cronbach Alpha coefficient of 0.86 for PSAQ, findings from the study revealed; Students' response shows they receive instruction in physics using educational CDs, radio, television and other digital material during post covid-19 era in learning SSII physics in Jos South LGA of Plateau State; The more instruction is given using ICT devices, it bridges the gap between abstract concepts and understanding them. Recommendations were made that: Students should be given more opportunities outside regular class hours (e.g., study labs or ICT clubs) to engage with computers and online resources. Government should put a modality that encourage all schools to utilize ICT in teaching and learning during pandemics that does not allow people to congregate by making policy in that regards and enforcing it.

Keywords: Post Covid-19 Era, Information Communication Technology, Learning, Physics

INTRODUCTION

The global education landscape had undergone a significant transformation in the wake of the covid-19 pandemic. The closure of schools and the necessity for remote learning have accelerated the adoption of Information Communication Technology (ICT) in education (Sahu, 2020). As schools gradually reopen in the post covid-19 era, understanding the impact of ICT on learning, particularly in the context of a challenging subject like Senior Secondary School Two (SSII) Physics, becomes crucial. The study focused on the post covid-19 era in Jos South L.G.A. Plateau State, Nigeria, examining the implications of integrating ICT devices in the learning processes of SSII Physics. Education systems worldwide faced unprecedented disruptions during the covid-19 era, with traditional classroom-based instruction giving way to remote and online learning. In the situation, ICT devices emerged as a lifeline, enabling educators to maintain continuity in learning. However, the effectiveness and implications of ICT integration in the learning of SSII Physics, a subject that traditionally relies heavily on practical demonstrations, need to be critically assessed within Jos South LGA, a part of the Jos-Bukuru metropolis in Plateau State, Nigeria, which was not exempted from the global shifts in education. Understanding the local

dynamics of implementing ICT in learning SSII Physics is essential for optimizing its benefits and addressing potential challenges. Jos South unique socio-economic and educational landscape warrants a specific investigation into the influence of ICT on SSII Physics learning in post covid-19 era.

From recent studies which underscores the growing importance of ICT in education globally, these technologies include online platforms, virtual laboratories, interactive simulations, and multimedia resources, which have shown promise in enhancing engagement and comprehension in various subjects in the post covid-19 era (Tyos & Fwangle, 2025; Clapp et al. 2017; Hamilton et al. 2019; Luckin et al. 2016). However, the application of these tools in the context of learning SSII Physics requires careful examination and adaptation to local conditions. Conversely, while ICT presents numerous opportunities for transforming SSII Physics learning, it also poses challenges such as contact inequalities, digital literacy gaps, and the need for teacher training. Identifying and addressing these challenges was pivotal in ensuring reasonable access to quality learning in Jos South. The integration of Information Communication Technology (ICT) in learning processes, especially in the situation of SSII Physics, has become an essential aspect of educational strategies in post covid-19 era.

Despite the global recognition of the potential benefits of ICT in learning, there remains a significant gap in our understanding of its specific impact on SSII Physics learning in post covid-19 era in Jos South LGA, Plateau State, Nigeria. Physics being taught at senior secondary school level has branches which include; mechanics, light, waves, electricity, and nuclear Physics, hence it needs special care and attention at all levels. Physics stands as one of the core scientific disciplines, primarily focused on uncovering the principles that govern the behavior of the universe. Often regarded as the foundation of all-natural sciences, physics explores universal laws and the intricate relationships among various physical phenomena. Its scope ranges from the study of vast galaxies to the tiniest subatomic particles. The knowledge acquired from studying physics extends to numerous professional and scientific fields, including engineering, manufacturing, mining, and construction. Supporting this view, Chukwunye and Adegoke (2014) emphasized that physics knowledge meaningfully contributes to a nation's economic growth and development. This underscores the critical importance of delivering physics instruction effectively. The influence of physics in daily life is far-reaching, making it essential for individuals especially in today's digital world to possess a basic understanding of its principles. Practical applications of physics in action include the wave circulation of blood through the body via veins and arteries, the uptake of water and nutrients by plants through capillarity action, and variations in weather patterns related to temperature and pressure all of which illustrate physics in everyday experience. Therefore, the teaching and learning of physics in senior secondary schools must be handled with care and precision, as the experiences provided by physics educators are vital. Zubairu et al. (2025) noted that many students perceive physics as a difficult and abstract subject, largely due to ineffective teaching methods. However, with the integration of modern ICT, this perception can change. Complex concepts can be more easily understood through the use of educational technology. Tools such as educational software offer visual and interactive means of instruction, helping students grasp difficult concepts and develop skills that may otherwise be challenging to learn through traditional methods.

Regardless of the importance of ICT in teaching and learning physics, the attitude and perception of students' offering physics in integrating ICT devices in learning had been a thing of great concern. Students' attitude towards the use of ICT in learning physics affects the students either positively or negatively, depending on the direction of the attitude (Macgilchrist, et al. 2020). Over the years, ICT used in learning physics in senior secondary school had been marred by several factors. Some of these factors include; poor ICT infrastructure in school, lack of steady power supply, lack of ICT training for teachers and lack of time as school hours operate between 8:00am to 2:00pm in most schools. Information and

Communication Technology (ICT) is an lengthy term for information technology (IT) which stresses the part of combined communications and incorporation of telecommunications (telephone lines and wireless signals), computers as well as necessary software, its storage and the audio-visual systems, which enable all users to access, store, transmit, and manipulate information.

Furthermore, students' use of ICT tools is often influenced by various attitudes and behavioral tendencies. Research indicates that female students tend to display more positive attitudes toward ICT compared to their male counterparts (Erdogd & Erdogd, 2022). Additionally, learners in private schools generally exhibit greater interest in ICT usage than those in public institutions. Students who frequently use ICT for recreational activities outside of the classroom are also more inclined toward using it for educational purposes. Interestingly, those with a heightened fear of failure are more motivated to engage with ICT (Erdogd & Erdogd, 2022). A separate study by Zhwan et al. (2015) found a significant attitudinal difference between Arts and Science students, favoring the latter, but reported no statistically significant relationship between students' academic performance and their attitudes toward ICT. However, students with average academic performance demonstrated higher emotional attachment to ICT compared to those with satisfactory performance. These findings offer valuable insights for policy makers and education researchers seeking to understand the key variables influencing students' technology use in learning contexts (Zhwan, 2015).

Importantly, the part of ICT in facilitating effective learning, especially during the covid-19 pandemic, became increasingly evident. Many educational institutions implemented digital platforms to maintain instructional continuity during lockdowns. This shift from traditional face-to-face instruction to e-learning led to the development and implementation of new educational concepts, including online education, virtual universities, e-books, and digital libraries, enabling students to learn based on their individual preferences (Tyos & Fwangle, 2025). The relevance of ICT was heightened during the pandemic, which significantly disrupted economies and sectors globally. Among all sectors, education was one of the few that transitioned almost entirely to online delivery. The integration of ICT into teaching and learning provided both students and teachers with the means to continue educational activities under strict social distancing guidelines. According to Mayhoob (2020), virtual learning emerged as the most viable solution for sustaining education during the pandemic, given that conventional teaching methods were no longer feasible and academic progress stalled in many parts of the world, including Nigeria. In recent years, innovative teaching methods for science subjects like physics have emerged, challenging the long-standing dominance of traditional pedagogies in Nigeria (Zhwan et al., 2015). The evolution toward e-learning spurred by the global pandemic has become widespread in educational institutions globally, with some schools compelled to adopt digital technologies due to the urgent need created by covid-19. Nevertheless, in many Nigerian public secondary schools, e-learning remains relatively underutilized (Kyari et al., 2018). The pandemic exposed critical weaknesses in the Nigerian education system, particularly in the delivery of science instruction. The outbreak of covid-19 in 2020 caused significant disruption, especially in science education, as the existing teaching models proved inadequate for the circumstances. Thus, the best solution to this was integration of ICT in teaching and learning of science subjects, especially SSII physics. In view of the foregoing, this study investigates the impact of ICT in learning SSII physics during the post covid-19 era in Jos South, Plateau State, Nigeria.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The outbreak of the Covid-19 pandemic led to an unprecedented disruption in educational systems globally, forcing a shift from traditional face-to-face instruction to digital and remote learning approaches. In Nigeria, particularly in Jos South,

Plateau State, this shift revealed critical gaps in the integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in the learning process, especially in science subjects like physics. Despite global recognition of ICT as a powerful tool for enhancing educational delivery, many public and private secondary schools in the region struggled to adapt effectively during and after the pandemic. Challenges such as inadequate digital infrastructure, lack of trained personnel, limited internet access, and minimal governmental support hindered the smooth implementation of ICT-based learning. Furthermore, a significant number of physics teachers exhibited low levels of ICT literacy, lacking basic computer operation skills necessary for virtual instruction, as noted by John (2020). These limitations not only affected the quality of SSII physics learning during the pandemic but also persisted into the post-covid-19 era, undermining efforts to modernize science education and improve student learning outcomes.

Given the practical and theoretical significance of physics in scientific and technological advancement, its effective teaching requires dynamic and interactive instructional methods many of which are ICT-driven. However, the degree to which ICT had currently influenced students' learning of physics in the post-covid-19 educational landscape remains unclear. This concern is particularly pressing in Jos South, Plateau State, where anecdotal evidence suggests inconsistent or insufficient use of ICT tools in the classroom.

Therefore, this study seeks to investigate the level to which ICT has influenced the learning of SSII physics in the post-covid-19 era, focusing on the current realities, challenges, and opportunities in public and private secondary schools in Jos South. Understanding this influence is essential for informing policy, teacher development, and the integration of technology in science education.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The study examined the influence of information communication technology on learning SSII physics in post covid-19 era in Jos South, Plateau State, Nigeria. The study was specifically set to:

- i. Investigate the level to which students offering physics implemented ICT devices use during post covid-19 era.
- ii. Evaluate the level of attitudes displayed by students offering physics to use of ICT devices while learning in the post covid-19 era.
- iii. Assess the level of challenges faced by students when using ICT devices in learning physics in post covid-19 era.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The study was guided by the following questions:

- i. What level do students offering physics used ICT devices in learning during the post covid-19 era?
- ii. What level of attitudes were displayed by students offering physics to use of ICT devices while learning in the post covid-19 era?
- iii. What level of challenges was faced by students when using ICT devices in learning physics in post covid-19 era?

LITERATURE REVIEW

This study is anchored in George Siemens' Connectivism Theory, introduced in 2004 (Siemens, 2007). The theory presents a framework for learning that aligns with the major transformations in modern society, emphasizing that learning is no longer an isolated, individual endeavor. Siemens and Downes are key figures in the development of this theory. Downes

focused on connective knowledge, which emphasizes the interactive and networked nature of learning (Downes, 2007). The way individuals operate and learn has evolved with the adoption of new technological tools, especially in the aftermath of the covid-19 pandemic, which shifted everyday activities from physical interaction to virtual engagement. Connectivism highlights the skills and competencies required for learners to succeed in a digitally driven world. Siemens describes it as a learning pattern designed for the digital age, following earlier theories such as behaviorism, cognitivism, and constructivism (Siemens, 2007). The theory underlines the importance of connectivity and communication essential components for effective instruction making it highly relevant to the learning of Senior Secondary Two (SSII) Physics. In an era when physical gatherings were restricted, continuous interaction through online platforms enabled students to access new knowledge and maintain consistent learning. Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has been defined in multiple ways by scholars, but all definitions commonly emphasize three core elements: information, communication, and technology. ICT can be described as the use of digital systems, particularly electronic computers, to process and manage information. This includes the storage, retrieval, conversion, and transmission of data (Ifueko, 2011).

The coronavirus disease (Covid-19) is a transmissible respiratory illness caused by a novel coronavirus strain. Initially reported to the World Health Organization (WHO) on December 31, 2019, in Wuhan, China, the virus was officially identified by Chinese authorities on January 7, 2020. W.H.O declared covid-19 a global pandemic on March 11, 2020. As of May 12, 2020, the Center for Systems Science and Engineering (CSSE) at Johns Hopkins University (JHU) reported over 4.3 million confirmed cases across more than 212 countries, with over 292,000 deaths and more than 1.6 million recoveries. By May 13, 2020, Europe had the highest number of cases at 1,675,742 with 155,762 deaths, followed by North America with 1,544,436 cases and 93,190 deaths, Asia with 701,532 cases and 22,851 deaths, and South America with 335,624 cases and 18,108 deaths (Dong, Hongru, & Lauren, 2020). In response to the rapid spread, lockdown measures were implemented globally, including in Nigeria, to mitigate transmission.

The lockdown measures implemented in Nigeria as a response to the covid-19 pandemic had a profound impact on science education. The effects on the nation's educational sector were significant and concerning (Sahu, 2020). Not long after the virus was detected in Nigeria, it rapidly spread across nearly all States. In an effort to control transmission, the government mandated the closure of all schools and enforced social distancing protocols. Consequently, the shift to online education became the only feasible alternative. Most States enforced lockdowns to protect their populations from the spread of the virus, which accelerated the move toward digital learning platforms during the pandemic. The period highlighted the limitations of traditional face-to-face teaching methods, especially in times of pandemic catastrophe. Physical interaction between teachers and students an essential component of science education was not possible. As a result, schools were shut down for extended periods, leading to major disruptions in the teaching and learning process (UNESCO, 2020). To address these challenges, the Nigerian government adopted e-learning strategies as a necessary solution during the prolonged school closures. While digital learning was not entirely new to Nigeria's educational system, its effective delivery and overall quality became critical concerns.

Sari and Nayir (2020) pointed out that several factors hinder the effective integration of ICT in teaching and learning. These obstacles can originate from students, teachers, or the educational institutions themselves. For instance, student readiness and attitude towards ICT use in schools have not been fully established. If educators themselves do not actively incorporate ICT into their teaching practices, it becomes unlikely that students will be encouraged to do so. Some students may also face anxiety or resistance toward technology commonly referred to as technophobia particularly at the beginning of

their academic journey (Sari & Nayir, 2020). Nevertheless, research by Zhwan et al. (2015) shows that students studying physics generally have a positive outlook on using ICT tools, although this perception can differ between male and female students.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted descriptive survey research design with three objectives and research questions respectively, with the population of 5,500 students in Jos South L.G.A. Plateau State, Nigeria. A sample size which consists of respondents taken through random sampling among students offering physics in Senior Secondary School Two (SSII) from six senior secondary schools out of eighteen public schools and five from private schools in Jos South LGA for the study making a total of eleven schools with twenty students per school resulting to a sample size of 220 respondents. The researchers used ‘Physics Student’s Assessment Questionnaire (PSAQ)’ for data collection which adapted the Likert scale and modified it to level for this study. The PSAQ had fifteen items with the following response modes Very High Level (VHL) = 5 points, High Level (HL) = 4 points, Moderate Level (ML) = 3 points, Low Level (LL) = 2 points and Very Low Level (VLL) = 1 point. The instrument was validated by experts from the Department of Science and Technology Education, University of Jos. The reliability of the instruments was obtain using Cronbach Alpha, which has a coefficient of 0.86. Data was collected using the questionnaire and computed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). Mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions with a decision ruled by real limits of numbers.

RESULTS

The results and interpretation are presented in tables with discussion following thereafter here below on the research questions;

Answering Research Question One: What level do students offering physics used ICT devices in learning during the post covid-19 era?

Table 1: Responses on the use of ICT Devices by Students offering Physics during Post Covid-19 era

S/N	Statement	N	\bar{X}	SD	Remark
1.	Computers	220	3.40	1.70	ML
2.	Radio and audio CDs	220	3.50	1.35	HL
3.	Television and video CDs	220	3.50	0.97	HL
4.	Mobile phones and e-mail	220	2.90	1.45	LL
5.	Physics educational soft wares	220	3.80	1.32	HL
Grand mean and standard deviation			3.42	1.36	ML

Key: X=mean, N=number of students, SD= Standard Deviation, VHL= very High Level, HL=High Level from 3.50-5.00, ML=Moderate Level from 3.00-3.4 and LL=Low Level from 0.50-2.99

Table 1 shows the mean score result on students’ responses on the level students adopted in the used ICT to learn Physics in post covid-19 era in Jos South LGA of Plateau State. From the result, items 1, 2, 3 and 5 have mean scores (\bar{X} =3.50, 3.50 & 3.80) High Level (HL), indicating that in post covid-19 era students use radio and audio CDs, television and video CDs and Physics educational software to learn while item one shows that computers were moderately used in post covid-19 with mean score of 3.40. Item 4 have mean score (\bar{X} =2.90) Low Level (LL), which means that students do not use

mobile phones and e-mail to learn Physics during post covid-19 era in Jos South LGA of Plateau State. Since the cumulative mean of 3.42 (ML), it implies that student’s adopted ICT devices for learning SSII Physics in post covid-19 era to a moderate level.

Answering Research Question Two: What level of attitudes were displayed by students offering physics to use of ICT devices while learning in the post covid-19 era?

Table 2: Responses on Attitude of Students’ Offering Physics Towards using ICT Devices to Learn in During Post Covid-19 era

S/N	Statement	N	\bar{X}	SD	Remark
1.	ICT supports learning and makes it more effective	220	4.40	0.87	HL
2.	The use of ICT makes learning more enjoyable	220	4.27	1.07	HL
3.	Use of ICT may slow down syllabus coverage in physics	220	2.71	1.38	LL
4.	I have a negative attitude towards the use of ICT	220	2.12	1.16	VLL
5.	I am afraid of using ICT devices for learning	220	2.25	1.34	VLL
Grand mean & S. D		3.15	1.16	ML	

Key: X=mean, N=number of students, SD= Standard Deviation, VHL= very High Level, HL=High Level from 3.50-5.00, ML=Moderate Level from 3.00-3.4 and LL=Low Level from 0.50-2.99

Table 2 shows the mean score result on responses on attitude of students’ offering physics towards using ICT devices in learning during post covid-19 era in Jos South LGA in Plateau State. From the result, items 1 and 2 have mean scores (\bar{X} =4.40 & 4.27) HL, indicating that ICT devices supports learning and makes it more effective and enjoyable. Also, items 3, 4 and 5 have mean scores (\bar{X} =2.71, 2.12 & 2.25) LL, this means that students do not agree with those statements which says: Use of ICT may slow down syllabus coverage in physics; I have a negative attitude to the use of ICT devices; and, I am afraid of using ICT devices for lessons. Since the cumulative mean of 3.15 (showed a moderate level), it implies that physics students’ have a moderate level positive attitude in using ICT devices in learning SSII physics during post covid-19 era in Jos South LGA of Plateau State.

Answering Research Question Three: What level of challenges was faced by students when using ICT devices in learning physics in post covid-19 era?

Table 3: Students Responses on challenges of using ICT in Teaching Physics during Covid-19 era

S/N	Statement	N	\bar{X}	SD	Remark
1.	We do not have ICT facilities to engage in e-learning	220	2.98	1.46	LL
2.	I am scared of using ICT to learn, I prefer the old method	220	1.98	1.09	VLL
3.	Our physics teachers do not have the required skills to use ICT	220	1.84	0.92	VLL
4.	Frequent power failure/ blackout could not allow the use of ICT during COVID19 Pandemic era	220	3.16	1.48	ML
5.	Inadequate time to use computer in class	220	3.61	1.35	HL
Grand mean and S. D		2.71	1.26	LL	

Key: X=mean, N=number of students, SD= Standard Deviation, VHL= very High Level, HL=High Level from 3.50-5.00, ML=Moderate Level from 3.00-3.4 and LL=Low Level from 0.50-2.99

Table 3 shows the mean score result on students' responses on challenges of using ICT devices in learning SSII physics during post covid-19 era in Jos South LGA of Plateau State. From the result, items 4 and 5 have mean scores (\bar{X} =3.61) HL, indicating that inadequate time to use computers in class and frequent power failure/blackout are challenges of using ICT devices in learning SSII Physics was high level. Items 1, 2 and 3 have low level, it means that students are not in agreement with those statements, it then implies that there are ICT facilities to engage in e-learning, students are not scared of using ICT to learn, as students are highly interested in ICT devices in learning processes, students prefer the use of ICT to old method of teaching Physics and that physics teachers have the required skills to use ICT devices. Since the cumulative mean of 2.71 is low level, it implies that students are having much challenges of using ICT devices in learning physics during post Covid-19 era in Jos South LGA of Plateau State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study assessed the influence of information communication technology in learning SSII Physics in post covid-19 era in Jos South LGA of Plateau State. The result of the findings shows that students receive instruction in SSII Physics using CDs and other digital materials during post covid-19 era in Jos South LGA of Plateau State, also students prefer learning using ICT devices and that students have bridge between physics concepts and learning which support the findings of (Tyos & Fwangle, 2025; N.T.I, 2015). Findings has also shown that students offering Physics has a positive attitude towards using ICT in learning during post covid-19 era in Jos South LGA Plateau State, as reinforced by the studies of Zhwan et al. (2015).

The results obtain from the level to which students offering Physics adopted the use of ICT devices in learning during post covid-19 pandemic era was rated high level. On challenges of using ICT devices, results from the research showed that: There are ICT facilities to engage in e-learning, students are not scared of using ICT to learn, students prefer the use of ICT to old method of learning Physics and that physics teachers have the required skills to use ICT devices. Since the cumulative mean of 2.71 is low level, it implies that students are having challenges of using ICT devices in learning SSII physics during post covid-19 era in Jos South LGA of Plateau State. This assertion on challenges faced in utilizing ICT is being reinforced by the studies of researchers like (Tyos & Fwangle, 2025; Sahu, 2020; Sari & Nayir, 2020)

The summary of the results reveals that: Students prefer and use ICT tools to receive instruction in SSII Physics during post covid-19 era in Jos South LGA of Plateau State from students' response which shows they receive instruction in physics using educational CDs, radio, television and other digital material during post covid-19 era in learning SSII physics in Jos South LGA of Plateau State. The findings show that majority of students had positive attitude towards using ICT devices in learning during post covid-19 era in Jos south LGA of Plateau State. Student's response show that ICT devices were utilize to a high level in learning SSII physics during post covid-19 era in Jos South LGA Plateau State.

CONCLUSIONS

The study concluded that the more instruction was given using ICT devices; it bridges the gap between abstract concepts and understanding them. Also revealed by research was the high level to which students employed using ICT devices on learning SSII physics during post covid-19 pandemic era, and further revealed by the study is the positive attitude of majority of SSII Physics students in using ICT devices for learning.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study it is recommended that:

1. Since mobile phones and emails were underutilized despite their accessibility, schools and policymakers should integrate mobile learning platforms into physics instruction pandemics such as covid-19. Workshops and orientation programs should be organized for students to boost competence and confidence in using smartphones and email for academic purposes. Although some ICT tools like radio and television are being used effectively, there is a need to invest in more interactive digital platforms (e.g., simulation apps and e-learning portals) to further enrich the learning experience in SSII physics. Given the high use of physics educational software, schools should procure and install more such packages and ensure they align with the SSII physics curriculum.
2. Since students show willingness and appreciation for ICT in learning, schools should leverage this by embedding more technology-based instruction in classroom practices. Learning platforms with interactive features (e.g., educational games, quizzes, badges) can increase enjoyment and reinforce positive attitudes. Educators should receive training in pedagogical approaches that integrate ICT, helping to further promote and normalize its use in the classroom.
3. The government and school administrators should invest in alternative power sources like solar panels to ensure uninterrupted ICT usage. Physics periods should also be adjusted to allow sufficient time for ICT-based instruction. Students should be given more opportunities outside regular class hours (e.g., study labs or ICT clubs) to engage with computers and online resources. Even though students believe teachers are skilled, ongoing training is essential to ensure teachers remain up-to-date with current digital tools in physics education. The Ministry of Education and school authorities should revise physics curricula to formally incorporate ICT-based methods and tools. A structured plan should be developed for sustained ICT usage across topics in the physics syllabus. Government should put a modality that encourage all schools to utilize ICT in teaching and learning during pandemics that does not allow people to congregate by making policy in that regards and enforcing it.

REFERENCES

- Chukwunenye, J. N. & Adegoke, B. A. (2014). Catching students' interest in physics practical using computer simulated experiment. *West African Journal of*, XXXIV, 297-309.
- Clapp, E. P., Ross, J., Ryan, J. O. & Tishman, S. 2017. *Maker-centered Learning: Empowering Young People to Shape Their Worlds*. San Fransisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.
- Dong, E.; Hongru, D. & Lauren, G. (2020). COVID-19 in Real Time. *Lancet Infect. Dis.* 2020, 3099, 19–20. [CrossRef]
- Downes, S. (2007). *What connectivism is? Half an hour*. <https://halffanhour.blogspot.com2007/02what-connectivism-is-.html>
- Erdogd, F. & Erdogd, E. (2022). Understanding students' attitudes towards ICT. *Interactive Learning Environment*, 31(10), 7467-7485. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10494820.2022.2073455>
- Hamilton, A., Donald, R., Michael, T., & Mikkell, G. (2019). "Digital storytelling as a tool for fostering reflection." *Frontiers: The Interdisciplinary Journal of Study Abroad* 31 (1): 59–73.
- Ifueko, O. (2011). *Emerging issues in tax administration: The way forward a lecture delivered at the 4th National Conference of Dept. of Financial Faculty of Business Administration*, University of Lagos on 12th.
- Izaak, H. W. (2015). The correlation study of interest at physics and knowledge of mathematics basic concepts towards the ability to solve physics problems of 7th grade students at junior high school in Ambon Maluku province, Indonesia.

- John, J (2020). Challenges of teacher's ICT skills during COVID-19. *Journal of Educational Technology Development and Exchange*, 12(1), 1-15.
- Kyari, S., Adiuku-Brown, M., Abechi & Adelokun, R. (2018). E-learning in tertiary education in Nigeria. Where do we stand? *International Journal of Education and Evaluation*. 4(9), 1-10.
- Luckin, R., Wayne, H., Mark, G. & Laurie, B. F. (2016). *Intelligence Unleashed*. An Argument for AI in Education.
- Macgilchrist, F., Allert, H. & Bruch, A. (2020) Students and society in the 2020s. Three future 'histories' of education and technology, *Learning, Media and Technology*, 45 (1), 76-89. DOI: 10.1080/17439884.2019.1656235
- Mayhoob, M. (2020). Challenges of E-learning during Covid-19 pandemic experienced by EPL learners. *Arab World English Journal*, 1, 351-362.
- NTI (2015). *Computer society. CIT 101. N.T.I year one module for computer education students*. Kaduna N.T.I. Press
- Sahu, P. (2020). Closure of universities due to Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19): Impact of education and mental health of students and academic staff. *Cureus*, 12 <https://doi.org/10.7554>.
- Sari, T., & Nayir, F. (2020). Challenges in distance education during the COVID-19 pandemic period. *Qualitative Research in Education*, 9(3), 325-360. <https://doi.org/10.17583/qre.2020.5872>
- Siemen's, G. (2007). Connectivism: A learning theory for the digital age. *International Journal of Instructional Technology and distance learning*, 2(1), 3-10. https://www.itdl.org/Journal/Jan_05/article01.htm
- Tyos, D. D & Fwangle, I. I. (2025). Impact of Information Communication Technology (ICT) on teaching physics in post covid-19-era in Jos South, Plateau State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Research in Science, Technology and Mathematics Education (IJRSTME) conference paper*, 11(1), 11-19.
- UNESCO (2020). 1.37 Billion students now ta home as Covid-19 school closures expand UNESCO. <https://unesco.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000376061/>
- Zhwan D. A., Azidah, B. A. Z., Raimi B. C. A., & Khalid, I. M. (2015). Students' attitudes towards information technology and the relationship with their academic achievement. *Contemporary Educational Technology*, 6(4), 338-354.
- Zubairu, A., Idena, G. O., & Zainab, M. (2025). Comprehensive review of the integration of ICT in improving physics education. *Journal of Educational technology*, 9 (5), 99-110.